

The economics of hydrogen production: The case of a GEN-IV reactor coupled with a high-temperature electrolysis plant

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ABSTRACT

High-Temperature Steam Electrolysis (HTSE) is a hydrogen production process requiring thermal and electrical power. From a technical standpoint, Nuclear Power Plants (NPPs) can provide the thermal and electrical power needed for an HTSE plant. This work reports an economic analysis to estimate the Levelized Cost Of Hydrogen (LCOH) by integrating HTSE in an NPP Balance-Of-Plant (BOP). The key novelties concerning the minimal literature on this topic are: (A) we used the ALFRED reactor, a Gen IV demonstrator of lead technology (LFR), and detailed HTSE plants as a case for the NPPs, to estimate capital and operational costs of coupling the nuclear and the HTSE plants; (B) we considered hydrogen cogeneration, with the LFR connected to the grid and not solely to the hydrogen plant; (C) we utilized actual data for the electricity price and optimized the NPP management by considering producing hydrogen when the electricity price is low (usually nighttime) and producing electricity for the grid when its price is high (peak hours). This enabled us to perform precise techno-economic analysis, comparing different configurations, estimating the LCOH, and evaluating the production time that minimizes it. Capital, operational, and opportunity costs are estimated, and, in the optimized scenarios, the LCOH is 5–6 \$/kg and produced for 17–18 h a day on average. Indeed, producing hydrogen for longer increases costs due to the loss of revenues from selling electricity during peak hours. An LCOH of 5–6 \$/kg is in the ballpark of other studies considering wind and solar but higher than fossil fuel-based production.

1. Introduction

Hydrogen is gaining increasing attention from industry and policy-makers because it can support decarbonization goals, particularly in hard-to-abate sectors, and has potential in long-term energy storage [1]. Yet, of the 95 million tons of global hydrogen produced in 2023, less than 1 million were derived from low-carbon sources [2]. Hydrogen from fossil fuels is usually produced by steam or CO₂ reforming of natural gas, by reforming of other hydrocarbons like methanol or benzene, or by gasification of coal [6,12]. Alternative production methods include splitting the water molecule by various means [6,12]. The first option is thermochemical cycles; the most common are sulfur-iodine, calcium-bromine, and copper-chlorine cycles. The second option is water splitting by electrolysis: the water molecule can be split using only electrical power at temperatures up to 300 °C; the electricity demand diminishes progressively at higher temperatures, and thermolysis happens around 2500 °C [1].

High-Temperature Steam Electrolysis (HTSE) is a process that requires electricity and heat as inputs and operates at 800 °C and beyond [1]. Globally, a rapidly growing number of projects have been announced, reflecting the current interest in HTSE, and today, the size of the largest HTSE operational plants is 4–8 MWe [12]. The modular nature of HTSE represents an important advantage [5]. Given the need for electrical and thermal power, HTSE modules could be coupled with a power plant that can provide both. Nuclear Power Plants (NPPs) can satisfy such requirements, are CO₂-free, and economically, this coupling is interesting. Indeed, most NPP-related costs are either CAPEX-sunk cost (capital expenditure, e.g., construction cost) or OPEX-fixed cost (operational expenditure, e.g., workforce salaries or insurance). So, NPPs are "price takers" in the electricity market, i.e., driven by the low marginal cost, NPPs have to sell electricity even if the market price is low. By coupling NPP with HTSE, part of the NPP's electricity and heat could be produced as input for the HTSE plant when the price of electricity in the market is low, while typical production and selling of

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electricity usually occur when the market price is high. This has several advantages, including:

- **Economic benefit.** Operating an NPP at a power lower than the nominal one (e.g., during a period of low demand or high production from renewable sources), reducing the load factor, does not offer economic advantages: capital costs are sunk costs, and operating costs are independent of the power output, so the critical point is maximizing revenues [3,4];
- **Lower thermo-mechanical stresses on reactor components.** This is due to the more constant core thermal power, which is not required to curtail electricity production, especially in case of load following by cogeneration [3,4];
- **Differentiation of the output.** The NPP produces both electricity and hydrogen that could provide an additional revenue stream, maximized according to the current market price of electricity and hydrogen.

Most of the operable NPPs today are Light Water Reactors (LWRs). Such Gen II, III/III+ NPPs can provide a steam temperature of around 300 °C, which could cover the needs for low-temperature hydrogen production [7]. For the higher temperature domain, such as HTSE operating ones, coupling with conventional NPP is still possible [23]; however, a better solution would be coupling with reactors reaching higher temperatures, like Gen IV ones [5,7]. They have either supercritical water or other fluids as coolants, reaching 500–800 °C and even 1000 °C in the primary cycle [7], thus, are suitable heat sources for HTSE. However, for safety reasons, the transfer of heat to the HTSE modules would happen from the secondary cycle of the reactor by extracting a fraction of the vapor flow rate. In this way, the NPP could perform load following by cogeneration of hydrogen by extracting more or less vapor, depending on the hydrogen plant requirements and the electricity price.

Among the Gen IV technologies, one of the most advanced in research is the Lead-cooled Fast Reactor (LFR), cooled by pure Pb or Pb-Bi Eutectic (LBE). These coolants give high margins for coolant boiling, can work at room pressure, and have excellent shielding properties [9]. An advanced design available for LFRs is ALFRED [8], the European demonstrator reactor cooled by pure Pb and planned for construction in Romania [8]. It has thermal and electrical nominal powers of 300 MWth and 120 MWe, respectively, and reaches a steam temperature of around 450 °C [8]. Such high temperatures in the secondary side are preferred for hydrogen cogeneration via HTSE when compared to conventional NPPs, but an intermediate process must be introduced in the configuration to integrate the HTSE system in the plant efficiently and feasibly [10]. The hydrogen production modules require the injection of high-temperature superheated steam and hydrogen mixture and a sweep gas. These high-energy streams are obtained via regenerative heat exchangers and electric heaters, to adjust the steam temperature to the operating point of the electrolyzer (this penalizes the overall hydrogen production efficiency) [10]. The main heat source of the process is the superheated steam produced by ALFRED, and the intermediate fluid is a thermal oil [10]. Despite the difference between the HTSE operating temperature and the ALFRED's steam one, it is possible to operate the HTSE system with a heat source at a lower temperature without resulting in strong over-costs [47], meaning that ALFRED and LFRs, in general, are suitable for this coupling.

This paper aims to establish the economic merit of hydrogen cogeneration through LFR and HTSE. Specifically, we selected the ALFRED design, and the detailed configurations reported in Ref. [11], to conduct the economic appraisal of the coupling between the reactor and the HTSE plant. In literature, only [13–15] study hydrogen production via LFR, but they do not perform an estimation of the hydrogen production cost or its levelized cost (LCOH) over the plant lifetime. Moreover, they do not consider hydrogen cogeneration, i.e., the thermal power of the nuclear reactor is entirely used by the hydrogen production

Table 1
Summary of the main methods to produce hydrogen.

Hydrogen production method	Requirements	Comments
Steam Methane Reforming [1,6]	Temperature: 700–1000 °C Pressure: 2.5–5 MPa	Technically and commercially well established. To produce 1 kg of H ₂ , 10 kg of CO ₂ are emitted.
Partial Oxidation of Hydrocarbons [1]	Temperature: 950–1100 °C Pressure: 3–7.5 MPa	It can accept all kinds of heavy hydrocarbons like oil, carbon, etc. Large-scale plants are available.
Coal Gasification [1,6]	Temperature: 600–1600 °C Pressure: 0.1–8 MPa	Widely diffused method. High CO ₂ emissions (even 30 kg of CO ₂ per 1 kg of H ₂).
Sulfur-Iodine Cycle (S-I) [1,6,35]	Temperature: 300–950 °C Pressure: 2–5 MPa	Series of complex chemical reactions. The cycle components must stand in very harsh environments. R&D is in progress to solve these issues and make the cycle commercially viable.
Copper-Chlorine Cycle (Cu-Cl) [1,6]	Temperature: 500–600 °C Pressure: atmospheric but some chemical processes may require higher pressures	Alternative to the high temperature of the SI cycle. Increased easiness in handling reagents but R&D is in progress to make it commercially viable.
Alkaline Water Electrolysis (AWE) [1,6,36,46]	Temperature: room temperature up to 120 °C Pressure: 0.1–3 MPa	Water molecules decompose under an electric field inside an electrolyzer. Proven, electricity-only application. Suitable for applications with fluctuating power.
Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) electrolysis [1,6,36,46]	Temperature: room temperature up to 120 °C Pressure: 0.1–3 MPa	Well-established technology. Suitable for applications with fluctuating power.
Anion Exchange Membrane (AEM) electrolysis [45]	Temperature: room temperature up to 100 °C Pressure: 0.1–3 MPa	Similar to PEM but for OH ⁻ instead of H ⁺ , faces low ionic conductivity but uses non-metal catalysts
Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cells (SOEC) [1,6,12,46]	Temperature: 700–1000 °C Pressure: atmospheric	Reduces electricity requirement with an increased temperature. Operational plants are available on the MW scale. It is used for the High-Temperature Steam Electrolysis (HTSE)

plant, while it has been shown how nuclear cogeneration would be profitable through appropriate scheduling of outages to periods of low-value electricity [38]. On the other hand, this work studies the 4 configurations detailed in Ref. [11], in which ALFRED is connected to the grid and the HTSE plant, enabling the reactor to perform cogeneration of hydrogen. An intermediate thermal oil loop connects the reactor secondary loop to 1–4 identical HTSE modules. Table 2 reports a comparison between the mentioned articles and this study.

According to Ref. [11], each HTSE module produces up to 0.203 kg/s of hydrogen; thus, we conduct the economic feasibility of such configurations, considering capital investment, Operation and Maintenance (O&M) costs, and losses from the electric power not sold to the grid but used for hydrogen production (opportunity cost). Specifically, the objectives of this work are the following.

- Estimate capital and O&M costs relevant to HTSE modules coupled with ALFRED;
- Estimate the LCOH and establish the optimized hydrogen production period that minimizes it;
- Analyze the differences among the configurations to understand the optimal number of HTSE modules;

Table 2
Comparison of this study with the articles found in the literature.

Article	Reactor	H ₂ production method	Work performed	Main outcomes
[13]	SSTAR-US (45 MWth)	Cu-Cl Cycle	Thermodynamic modeling of a single plant configuration in which the thermal energy of the reactor is fully used for H ₂ production. Implementation of the mass, energy, and exergy rate balance equations	Estimation of H ₂ and electrical power production of the plant, without any economic considerations
[14]	CLEAR-H (200 MWth)	HTSE	Analysis of a single plant configuration. The reactor is used solely as an electricity and heat source for the H ₂ plant	Estimation of H ₂ production, without any economic considerations
[15]	CLEAR-I (10 MWth)	Cu-Cl Cycle	Thermodynamic modeling of a single plant configuration in which the thermal energy of the reactor is fully used for H ₂ production. Determination of capital, O&M, and fuel costs	Estimation of H ₂ and electrical power production of the plant. Estimation of levelized cost of energy based on total costs and total production
This study	ALFRED (300 MWth, 119 MWe)	HTSE	Detailed estimation of CAPEX and OPEX of the plant using cost models and data from literature of 4 configurations, see Appendix. Estimation of opportunity cost using electricity price data of 4 countries	Determination of LCOH for any production time. Determination of optimized production time that reduces cost. Identification of optimal configuration

- Benchmark the LCOH of ALFRED + HTSE against production with fossil fuels, renewables, and other NPPs.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: section 2 provides a literature review on hydrogen production methods and hydrogen produced from NPPs; section 3 gives a detailed description of the methodology used for this economic analysis, including the main assumptions and the estimation process for all the costs; section 4 reports the results for each step of the analysis; it also includes a sensitivity analysis for the computed LCOH and some additional comments; and section 5 concludes the paper.

2. Literature review

2.1. Hydrogen production methods

This section provides a general overview of hydrogen production methods, followed by the production processes that could be integrated with NPPs. This section also reports the scientific articles related to hydrogen production with LFRs.

Table 1 summarises the most relevant hydrogen production methods. Fossil fuel-based methods are by far the most common. 62 % of global production came from natural gas, while 21 % from coal, without Carbon Capture (CC) [12]. Low-carbon alternatives accounted for less than 1 % [2]. The LCOH mainly causes this difference, with methane reforming and coal gasification being typically the cheapest options. Fossil fuel production can be coupled with CC to reduce greenhouse gas emissions for the so-called “blue-hydrogen”. Capture efficiencies as high as 99 % can be achieved [12], however, most of the facilities implementing CC operate at partial capture (only capturing the CO₂ in the syngas, and not the one resulting from fuel combustion in the furnace) with a capture rate of 40–60 % [12]. It could be possible to capture the CO₂ from the furnace exhaust at a levelized cost 50–60 % higher than the unabated one. In the automated reformer process, most of the CO₂ is available in the syngas, resulting in capture rates of 93–98 % [12].

Another route to produce hydrogen is water electrolysis [46]. Many technologies are available, with working temperatures ranging from room temperature to over 850 °C. Such technologies require heat, electricity, or both as inputs. Carbon and hydrocarbon-assisted electrolysis is a widely studied topic, and a comprehensive review is available in Ref. [17]. However, other means, including NPPs, can provide these inputs. Other hydrogen production methods are reported in Refs. [1] and [6]. Such methods are less common and account for a small fraction of the total production. A summary of the most common hydrogen production methods is available in Table 1.

2.2. Hydrogen from nuclear

Both conventional reactors (with heaters) and Gen IV high-

temperature reactors could reach the required process temperature [35–37]. Water electrolysis is the only available technology that provides low-carbon hydrogen with wide availability [38]. Considering low-temperature electrolysis, both AWE and PEM can be easily coupled with conventional and advanced NPPs, particularly Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) [5]. Off-peak production of nuclear hydrogen is an option [36,37] provided an appropriate scheduling of outages to periods of low electricity prices [38]. HTSE could be coupled with conventional reactors (with heaters) [23] and Gen IV high-temperature reactors [5]. In particular [23], performs a techno-economic analysis of retrofitting existing (large) LWRs to produce low-carbon hydrogen via HTSE. The study estimated the LCOH reporting values as low as 1.20 \$/kg [5]. It considers SMRs, a light-water one and a gas-cooled one, for load following by cogeneration of hydrogen and takes into account AWE, HTSE, and the S-I cycle, estimating the LCOH of the different configurations. Both [5] and [23] consider reactors that can switch between electricity production and hydrogen cogeneration, similar to this study, but with different technology and configurations. Other studies consider integrated energy systems including nuclear and hydrogen: [39] proposes a hydrogen production and storage system combining both nuclear and solar energy, and it considers both thermochemical water decomposition and electrolysis; while [40] demonstrate how hydrogen could be used as a commodity to boost revenues, grid stability, and flexibility of future generation NPPs in integrated nuclear-renewable grids.

Nuclear hydrogen from HTSE could produce less than 0.5 kgCO₂eq/kgH₂ [16]. Regarding thermochemical cycles, the Cu-Cl cycle could be coupled with both conventional and Gen IV NPPs [16,36], like LFRs [13] and supercritical water reactors [49]. However, it would generate three times the emissions of the HTSE process [16]. The S-I cycle could be coupled with Gen IV high-temperature reactors [43,50]. However, given the high-temperature requirements and complex chemical reactions, this seems unfeasible for other types of reactors [5]. An S-I plant could also have the problems of thermal inertia and low flexibility typical of large thermochemical facilities [5].

Regarding Scopus-indexed publications,¹ we performed a search in the literature resulting in 20 scientific publications. A screening process excluded articles referring to Gen IV reactors but only mentioning LFRs, as well as articles referring to LFRs but only mentioning the possibility of hydrogen production. After the screening process, three articles remain, summarized in Table 2:

- [13] reports the concept of an LFR coupled with a Cu-Cl cycle, which can produce 3.45 g/s of hydrogen and 467.2 kWe of electricity;

¹ Search string: “(“lead fast reactor” OR “lead cooled fast reactor” OR “lead cooled reactor”) AND “hydrogen”. Search date: 28/04/2025.

Fig. 1. Simplified configurations based on [11]. The number of HTSE modules varies between 1 and 4 (as in the figure). ALFRED BOP is connected to the HTSE modules via an intermediate thermal oil circuit (dashed).

Table 3
Main characteristics of the ALFRED-HTSE configurations, retrieved from Ref. [11].

	Unit	H1	H2	H3	H4	No H ₂ plant
Cycle gross power	MWe	127.1	125.5	123.8	122.2	128.5
Electric power required by HTSE	MWe	26.9	53.8	80.7	107.6	–
Thermal power required by HTSE	MWth	6.1	12.2	18.3	24.3	–
Power to the grid	MWe	89.5	60.9	32.4	3.8	118.9
Secondary water-steam-derived mass flow	kg/s	2.41	4.83	7.24	9.65	–
H ₂ production rate	kg/s	0.203	0.406	0.609	0.812	–
Electric power not sold during H ₂ production	MWe	29.4	58.0	86.5	115.1	–
Electric power not sold during hot-standby	MWe	1.4	3.0	4.7	6.3	–
Overall efficiency	%	39.40	39.47	39.54	39.60	39.63

- [14] reports the CLEAR-H concept, an LBE-cooled reactor that could reach a production of 47 tons/day of hydrogen by providing steam up to 600 °C with a thermal-to-hydrogen efficiency of 39 %;
- [15] analyzes a small LFR performance for hydrogen production, reporting a production of 2.34 g/s of hydrogen and 53.9 kWe of electricity at a levelized cost of 42.5 \$/MWh.

In this work, data on the thermophysical properties of the thermal cycle and dimensions of the various components are retrieved from Ref. [11]. Following [10] and [11], we analyze the HTSE technology, which is interesting given its production of greenhouse gases at least twenty times lower than fossil fuels [16], the number of global projects [12,30], and coupling potential with Gen IV NPPs with high efficiency [10]. We used the reported data to estimate hydrogen production, CAPEX, and OPEX of the HTSE plants. In this way, this study reports the estimation of LCOH over the plant lifetime, and in cogenerative

configurations, both aspects that are not present in the literature about hydrogen production via LFRs.

3. Methodology

This section provides an overview of the methodology used to calculate the LCOH. After describing the assumptions and the configurations selected, the methodology is divided into three parts: capital and O&M cost estimation, opportunity cost estimation, and determination of LCOH.

3.1. Hypothesis and plant configurations

The following are the main assumptions used in this work:

- **Configurations.** This study considers four configurations. Figure 1 reports their simplified representation based on the ones detailed in Ref. [11]. It is possible to have between 1 and 4 HTSE modules; thus, as a notation, we will use H1, H2, H3, and H4 for the different configurations. The number indicates the HTSE modules present in each of them. The maximum number of modules is 4 because 5 would require more electrical power than the one ALFRED could provide. The HTSE modules are coupled with ALFRED Balance-Of-Plant (BOP) via an intermediate thermal oil circuit, dashed in Figure 1. The number of modules does not influence how they are connected to the intermediate circuit; thus, no extra costs are coming from additional modules in the HTSE plant, beside the modules themselves and the different sizing of the heat transfer system. Table 3 reports the main characteristics of the configurations [11]. also reports the computations for the overall plant efficiency, and specifies that the total steam mass flow circulating in the secondary loop of the reactor is 193 kg/s. The maximum extracted steam mass flow (in configuration H4) is less than 10 kg/s, 5 % of the total mass flow. HTSE plant life is assumed to be 20 years [18].
- **Reference LFR plant.** The reference plant is ALFRED NPP. Its nominal electricity output to the grid is 118.9 MWe (Table 3); this plant's details are provided in Ref. [11] and in Table 3 as well.
- **'Differential' analysis.** Since the aim is to establish the economic merit of HTSE against the reference plant (i.e., the NPP, which only produces electricity), the costs expected in all configurations can be excluded. Given that they are not differential for the analysis (they do not vary among the four configurations), ALFRED NPP CAPEX and OPEX are excluded. These also include ALFRED BOP before the water-oil heat exchanger in Figure 1, assumed the same in all configurations. Costs that are included in the analysis are, e.g., the cost of the thermal oil intermediate circuit and the HTSE system.
- **Levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH).** This includes the additional investment required for the HTSE plant (the HTSE CAPEX), its O&M costs, and revenue losses due to reduced electricity output. The

Fig. 2. Conceptual scheme used to estimate hydrogen production cost.

technical details about the HTSE and ALFRED configurations are in Ref. [11]. The LCOH is a common value found in literature, so it will be useful to compare the results from this study to those from other studies.

- **Code of accounts.** To ensure all HTSE components are considered in the cost estimation, we developed a code of accounts for the HTSE following [20]. This code is detailed in the Appendix. It includes pre-construction, direct (including civil structures and improvements, HTSE plant equipment, thermal oil intermediate circuit, and other miscellaneous equipment), indirect, and O&M costs.
- **Electricity price data.** This study utilizes hourly electricity price data of four countries: Romania (host country for ALFRED [8]), Germany, France, and Italy, due to their different electricity price data and shares of production sources [26]. We retrieved 5 years of hourly data, from 2019 to 2023, from Ref. [26]. Prices were expressed in Euros or Romanian Lei and were transformed into 2022 USD. The exchange rates and inflation coefficients are reported in the Appendix. By using past data we avoid the estimation of future electricity share and price. NPPs operating in load following by cogeneration would perform better with high variability in electricity price at the same average electricity price (which could be the case for a larger share of renewables in future scenarios). Thus, this remains a conservative analysis. We also assume that in the HTSE lifetime (20 years) the electricity prices do not differ significantly from the 5 years retrieved.

Figure 2 represents schematically the model used for the hydrogen production cost estimation.

3.2. Cost estimation

The cost estimation for the different accounts is detailed in the Appendix. The Total Capital Investment (TCI) is the sum of the Direct Costs (DC), pre-construction costs, and all indirect costs. All costs and revenues are expressed in 2022 USD (\$), retrieving inflation and exchange rates from Ref. [19]. Regarding the hydrogen plant direct costs, the different accounts are evaluated as follows, with estimations based on the data and dimensions reported in Ref. [11]:

- **Structures and improvements.** Evaluated at 10% of the DC or 7% of the TCI [23].
- **HTSE equipment.** Includes modules and other related equipment. We evaluated their costs following [18]. The cost of the feedwater and heat transfer equipment (including the evaporator and tubing) is estimated using the models reported by Ref. [24], accounting for cost corrections due to material [25].

- **Thermal oil intermediate circuit.** Includes all equipment required for the intermediate loop. As for the previous point, we performed the cost evaluation following [24,25].
- **Other miscellaneous equipment.** Evaluated as a fraction of the TCI, 6% in this case [22].

To evaluate the cost of the accounts, we followed the economy-of-scale principle according to Ref. [21]. We assumed the plant is a First-Of-A-Kind (FOAK), and the affected accounts are increased by a fraction corresponding to the ratio of values reported in Ref. [22] for large NPPs (LWRs). The other hydrogen plant costs are evaluated as a fraction of the TCI [16]:

- The pre-construction costs at 1.5% of TCI;
- All indirect costs at 28.10% of TCI;
- Annual O&M costs (comprehending stack replacement, royalties, labor, planned and unplanned maintenance, overhead, insurance, and taxes) at 13% of TCI.

3.3. Determination of opportunity cost

The opportunity cost is a revenue reduction from the investor's perspective: the HTSE plant requires electrical power, and the NPP produces it. So, the utility that owns the NPP loses revenue from not selling such electricity to the market. The "potential revenue lost" is called "opportunity cost" in economic terms. To calculate the opportunity cost, we considered the electricity price data (2019–2023) of Romania, Germany, France, and Italy.

The optimized scenario is identified via an enumerative algorithm: hydrogen is produced for a generic amount of X hours, between 1 h and 5 years total (43824 h), and the production time corresponds precisely to the X hours of lowest electricity prices in the 5 years. This allows us to compute the opportunity cost for any arbitrary hydrogen production period. For each scenario, we can state:

- Hydrogen is produced for X hours. These hours have the lowest electricity prices in the considered 5 years;
- During these X hours, the electric power not sold (each hour) is between 29.4 and 115.1 MWe, depending on the configuration (Table 3);
- When the plant does not produce hydrogen, it remains in hot-standby mode for the remaining $Y = 43824 - X$ hours, in which the electricity prices are the highest in the considered 5 years;
- During these Y hours, the electric power not sold (each hour) is between 1.4 and 6.3 MWe, depending on the configuration (Table 3);

Table 4
Results of the cost estimation, reported in detail in the Appendix.

[M \$]	Pre-construction costs	Direct costs	Indirect costs	Total capital investment	Annual O&M costs
H1	1	60	24	86	11
H2	2	91	36	130	17
H3	2	117	47	166	22
H4	3	139	55	197	26

To compute the opportunity cost in these 5 years, for each hour, the amount of power not sold is multiplied by the corresponding electricity price.

3.4. Levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH)

Firstly, we can compute the “Total amount of Produced Hydrogen”, TPH, in the considered period. Each module produces 0.203 kg/s or 730.8 kg/h of hydrogen. This rate is multiplied by the production hours and the number of HTSE modules from 1 to 4. The LCOH is the sum of three different contributions: HTSE plant CAPEX, HTSE plant OPEX, and electricity costs (i.e., the opportunity cost).

It is assumed the CAPEX is equally distributed during the construction of the HTSE plant, assumed to be 2 years. Thus, the construction takes both year 1 and 2, while, considering an HTSE lifetime of 20 years, from year 3 to year 22, the HTSE modules produce hydrogen and have the annual OPEX as cash outflow. In the computation of the LCOH, eq. (2), the OPEX contribution is annually increased to account for inflation j , assumed 2 % [27].

The last component of the LCOH comes from the opportunity cost and depends on the electricity price, $C_{Opp.Cost}$. In principle, hydrogen production will occur during the period of lowest electricity prices; however, as TPH increases, hydrogen is produced at increasingly higher electricity prices. This component is high at low production because the hydrogen sales must cover the opportunity cost during hot standby periods. As the production increases, it decreases to a certain extent, reaches a minimum, and then increases again. This component is computed with eq. (1):

$$C_{Opp.Cost} = \left(P_{loss,H_2} \sum_{h=0}^{t_{H_2}} E_h + P_{loss,HSB} \sum_{h=t_{H_2}+1}^{43824} E_h \right) \frac{1}{5} \quad 1$$

P_{loss} indicates the electric power not sold during hydrogen production (subscript H_2) and hot standby (subscript HSB), t_{H_2} is the total time to produce the TPH in hours, and E is the electricity price in a specific hour h . We have $E_1 < E_2 < E_3 < \dots < E_{43824}$ based on the assumptions mentioned earlier. The factor 1/5 is added because, by considering the 5 years 2019–2023, the obtained value would be the average opportunity cost in a year. In this way, opportunity cost can be expressed as “annual” values to compute the LCOH and, later, to report the results.

The LCOH is then computed with eq. (2), EOC and EOL stand for “End Of Construction” (year 2) and “End Of Life” (year 22), respectively. The obtained LCOH curves have a minimum corresponding to the optimized production time that minimizes costs. This procedure is repeated for each configuration and country for a total of 16 times.

Table 5
Results of the opportunity cost calculations.

Production time per year	500 h				3000 h				6000 h				8760 h			
Hot-standby time per year	8260 h				5760 h				2760 h				0 h			
Opportunity cost [M\$]	H1	H2	H3	H4	H1	H2	H3	H4	H1	H2	H3	H4	H1	H2	H3	H4
France	2	3	5	7	4	9	13	18	11	22	32	43	32	63	95	126
Germany	1	3	4	6	4	8	12	16	10	20	30	40	29	57	85	112
Italy	2	5	7	9	6	12	17	23	14	28	42	56	38	74	111	147
Romania	2	3	5	7	4	8	13	17	10	20	30	40	29	57	85	114

Fig. 3. LCOH computed for France.

Fig. 4. LCOH computed for Germany.

$$LCOH = \frac{\sum_{y=1}^{EOL} \frac{C_{CAPEX,y} + C_{OPEX,y} \times (1+j)^y + C_{Opp.Cost,y}}{(1+j)^y}}{\sum_{y=EOC}^{EOL} \frac{TPH_y}{(1+j)^y}} \quad 2$$

4. Results and discussions

This section reports the results for each step. We also performed a sensitivity analysis and added comments and considerations regarding the LCOH obtained by other processes.

4.1. Capital, O&M, and opportunity costs

Table 4 includes the results from the cost estimation detailed in the Appendix. Configuration H4 is the most expensive as expected but benefits from economy-of-scale. Regarding the estimation of opportunity cost, Table 5 reports, as examples, the results obtained at 500, 3000, 6000 h and a full year of hydrogen production, though these values were computed for production times from zero hours to a full year. The absolute value of the opportunity costs increases from H1 to H4 (the power

Fig. 5. LCOH computed for Italy.

Fig. 6. LCOH computed for Romania.

Fig. 7. Comparison (a) and details of the minima (b) of the curves obtained for configuration H4.

Table 6
Optimized scenarios for the different configurations.

		H1	H2	H3	H4
France	Daily production time [h]	18.6	18.1	17.8	17.3
	Annual production time [h]	6800	6600	6500	6300
	Total H ₂ production in 1 year [ton]	4.97 × 10 ³	9.65 × 10 ³	1.43 × 10 ⁴	1.84 × 10 ⁴
	LCOH [\$/kg]	6.92	5.90	5.41	5.11
Germany	Daily production time [h]	19.5	18.9	18.4	18.1
	Annual production time [h]	7100	6900	6700	6600
	Total H ₂ production in 1 year [ton]	5.19 × 10 ³	1.01 × 10 ⁴	1.47 × 10 ⁴	1.93 × 10 ⁴
	LCOH [\$/kg]	6.64	5.66	5.20	4.90
Italy	Daily production time [h]	18.4	17.5	17.3	17.0
	Annual production time [h]	6700	6400	6300	6200
	Total H ₂ production in 1 year [ton]	4.90 × 10 ³	9.35 × 10 ³	1.38 × 10 ⁴	1.81 × 10 ⁴
	LCOH [\$/kg]	7.70	6.65	6.15	5.83
Romania	Daily production time [h]	19.7	19.2	18.6	18.4
	Annual production time [h]	7200	7000	6800	6700
	Total H ₂ production in 1 year [ton]	5.26 × 10 ³	1.02 × 10 ⁴	1.49 × 10 ⁴	1.96 × 10 ⁴
	LCOH [\$/kg]	6.62	5.65	5.19	4.89

requirements increase). Italy has the overall highest contribution, followed by France, while Germany and Romania have very similar ones.

4.2. Levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH)

The LCOH is now computed with eq. (2). Its minimum corresponds to the optimized production time. For every considered country, the optimal configuration is H4, as expected, despite having the highest capital investment and the largest opportunity cost. Figures 3–6 report the results for the configurations in France, Germany, Italy, and Romania.

Always producing hydrogen is not the optimal strategy to reduce its levelized cost. This is true because, in the case of high electricity prices, it is better to sell the electricity directly instead of using it to produce hydrogen. On average, hydrogen should be produced between 17 and 18 h each day to optimize cost. If the plant always produces hydrogen, its cost would increase by 25–30 % from the optimized value.

Table 6 summarises the optimized scenarios for each configuration. H4 is always the configuration with the lowest LCOH and daily production time, i.e., the average time that hydrogen should be produced daily. Figure 7 compares the curves obtained for configuration H4 for the different countries: it is possible to see how Germany’s and Romania’s curves are very similar, with France’s one being slightly higher, and Italy’s one being the highest. This configuration can produce 1.81–1.96 × 10⁴ tons of hydrogen in the optimized scenarios. This was expected due to the economy-of-scale of the HTSE plant and that the NPP does not drastically change among configurations. In 2023, the total amount of hydrogen produced from low-carbon sources was less than 1 million tons [2]. Thus, this plant alone could produce around 2 % of the global low-carbon hydrogen, considering 2023 consumption (which is likely to increase rapidly [2]). For a FOAK, the LCOH can only increase from these optimized values, and some reasons include: delays

Fig. 8. Sensitivity analysis, inputs are varied by ±10 %.

Table 7
Values used for efficiency variations [11].

Variable	Symbol	Value	Unit
Efficiency	ϵ	0.396	–
Power to the grid	P_{grid}	3.806	MWe
Reactor thermal power	Q_{th}	300.0	MWth
HTSE sweep gas inlet	P_{sweep}	0.369	MWth
HTSE process water	P_{water_in}	0.309	MWth
Hydrogen heating value	HV	141.9	MJ/kg
Hydrogen production rate	HPR	0.812	kg/s

and increased construction and O&M costs; the load factor of the plant (requiring shutdown); production of hydrogen during hours with higher electricity prices than expected; and production of hydrogen for more or less time than the optimized one.

4.3. Sensitivity analysis

Without losing generality, we focused on the H4 configuration with Romania’s electricity prices to perform the sensitivity analysis. We considered 10 % variations (positive and negative) on the following inputs: HTSE CAPEX and OPEX, overall plant efficiency, interest rate, inflation rate, and the power required by the HTSE modules during hot standby and hydrogen production. Only one input is changed at a time. Figure 8 reports the percentual variation after such changes from the minimum of 4.89 \$/kg (see Table 6).

The overall plant efficiency is calculated based on the power requirements of the HTSE, ALFRED thermal power, and hydrogen production [11]. For this analysis, the HTSE plant maintains the same power requirements regardless of the efficiency, i.e., the variation in the latter is caused solely by a proportional variation in the hydrogen production rate (e.g., in case of technology development and electrolyzer redesign). Particularly, from eq. (3) derived from Ref. [11], given a positive or negative 10 % variation in efficiency, the hydrogen production rate, from 0.812 kg/s, increases to 0.896 kg/s (+10.4 %) and decreases to 0.728 kg/s (−10.3 %):

$$HPR = \frac{\epsilon - \frac{P_{grid}}{Q_{th} + P_{sweep} + P_{water_in}}}{\frac{HV}{Q_{th} + P_{sweep} + P_{water_in}}} \quad 3$$

Using the values in Table 7 before the applied variation in efficiency [11].

We can note that a certain variation in plant efficiency would cause a similar one in terms of LCOH. Also, almost all the variations seem to be symmetric. The only one which is not is the HTSE ‘power required during production’. This happens because it could decrease by 10 % but cannot increase by 10 % because it would result in a power higher than the one available from ALFRED. Thus, it is asymmetric because it could only increase by about 3 % instead of 10 %. CAPEX and OPEX have an

impact of around 2 % and 3 %, respectively, while all the other inputs cause more minor variations. As expected, the LCOH decreases with the increase of the overall plant efficiency, and with the decrease of HTSE power requirements, CAPEX, OPEX, interest, and inflation rate.

4.4. Comparison of ALFRED-HTSE’s LCOH with alternative hydrogen production technologies

In the literature, we often find that the expected LCOH is similar to or lower for nuclear energy compared with what is computed here. However, most studies refer to large reactors or a fleet of SMRs [28]. considers a 500 MWe LWR and 4 × 100 MWe SMRs. The authors obtained, respectively, values below 2 and 4 \$/kg without any incentives and values of −0.50 and 0.98 \$/kg with a production tax credit of 3 \$/kg [29]. considers a 4 × 1200 MWe and a 4 × 1120 MWe NPPs, obtaining values between 3.18 and 6.17 \$/kg, including hydrogen transportation and storage [1]. reports values of around 1 \$/kg for nuclear with CC, 1.5 \$/kg for nuclear with steam methane reforming and CC, and 3.0–3.5 \$/kg for nuclear with electrolysis [1]. also reports four different case studies considering modular gas reactors, with LCOHs of 5–6 \$/kg, including transportation and storage. Another relevant study considering a gas reactor is [32]. It affirms that high-temperature gas reactors could become one of the cheapest options for hydrogen production in China by 2050. It considers different water electrolysis technologies, reporting an LCOH of 3–4 \$/kg in 2020, which would decrease to 1.5 \$/kg in 2050.

In this work, calculations are limited to a single small reactor, ALFRED, which limits the size of the HTSE. Because of the economy-of-scale, the larger the plant, the greater the hydrogen production rate and the lower its levelized cost. This observation is also reported by Ref. [1], which states that hydrogen from Gen IV nuclear could be justified for large hydrogen plants. However, most current HTSE projects require less than 1 MW of power [30].

These values for the LCOH are comparable with or lower than what is expected for renewable energy sources [1]. reports the following values for hydrogen produced from renewable energy sources: 2.5–3.0 \$/kg for solar photocatalysis, around 3.5 \$/kg for hydroelectric, 4.0 \$/kg for solar biomass, 4.5–5.0 \$/kg for wind, and around 11.5 \$/kg for solar photovoltaic [28]. reports values of 4.21 \$/kg for a 3.7 GW solar plant, 5.68 \$/kg for a 3.5 GW wind farm, and 3.82 \$/kg for a hybrid plant of 1.7 GW from solar and 1.8 GW from wind [31]. reports that the values retrieved from literature estimating the LCOH from electrolysis and renewables are between 2 and 8 \$/kg, with the median being 3.64 \$/kg. Also, the variable input of power from renewables could have a meaningful impact on energy consumption and the LCOH [42]: analyzes offshore wind-based hydrogen production from water electrolysis focusing on Australia with a time horizon of 2040. It reports an LCOH of 2–12 \$/kg. This great variability depends on the specific location of the plant, the rapid scaling up of the technology (required for economic competitiveness), the interest rate, and the cost of capital.

None of these scenarios, however, could compete today with the much more common processes from fossil fuels, which have LCOHs as low as 1 \$/kg, even with the increase in cost due to CC [41]. considers methane decomposition systems and steam methane reforming. The authors report 1.6–2.2 \$/kg and 1.0–1.2 \$/kg, respectively [30]. reports the LCOH of fossil fuels in China in 2018: around 1.75 \$/kg for natural gas, 2.25 \$/kg for natural gas with CC, 1 \$/kg for coal, and 1.5 \$/kg for coal with CC [33]. considers coal gasification and steam methane reforming in Western Canada, reporting values lower than 1.5 \$/kg for both of them, and, considering CC, these values would increase to around 2 \$/kg [31]. reports that, in literature, steam methane reforming without CC produces hydrogen with an LCOH of 0.7–2.3 \$/kg, with a median of 1.66 \$/kg. With CC, this last value increases to 2.09 \$/kg. The reported range for coal gasification without CC is 1.0–3.2 \$/kg with a median value of 1.84 \$/kg. With CC, this last value changes to 2.23 \$/kg [32]. analyzes different technologies in China in 2020–2050: assuming

Fig. 9. Summary of LCOHs from different sources.

raw materials maintain low prices, coal gasification, and steam methane reforming would provide an LCOH of 1.5 and 2.2 \$/kg, respectively. However, when carbon prices are introduced, these values increase, in 2050, to 2.0 and 2.5 \$/kg respectively [32]. Finally [1], reports around 1.5 \$/kg for steam methane reforming and coal, 1.5–2.0 \$/kg for steam methane reforming with CC, and around 2.5 \$/kg for coal with CC. Figure 9 is a summary of these values.

There are ways to make zero-carbon hydrogen more competitive, mainly depending on Government policies. The first way is to introduce a carbon tax (or a tax system reform), proportional to the greenhouse gases generated by the production methods, making low- or zero-carbon ones preferable [34,48]. A carbon tax of just over 100 \$/tCO₂ (tons of CO₂) would already have a significant impact, making conventional fossil fuel production methods less convenient than their CC counterparts [48], but also than other alternatives including nuclear [32]. Alternative ways may include incentives for hydrogen on a country or international level. Externalities may also play a relevant role in increasing the ‘true’ hydrogen cost [44]: addresses these aspects by focusing on resource depletion, ecosystem quality, and human health. The authors report that hydrogen from nuclear is the least affected by such externalities, meaning it would become very competitive if the electrolyzer’s CAPEX and electricity generation costs decreased. The last point is that, for now, we can only say that the hydrogen market has the potential to increase tens or hundreds of times [1,2]. With the development of the market, new policies would be established.

5. Conclusion

This study performs an economic analysis of HTSE hydrogen plants inserted in ALFRED BOP to estimate the levelized cost of hydrogen. It analyzes 4 configurations with 1–4 HTSE modules, each requiring 26.9 MWe, heat from the vapor of the secondary side of the NPP, and producing 0.203 kg/s of hydrogen each. The LCOH takes into account the capital and operational costs of the HTSE plant, the opportunity cost, and the total hydrogen production. We evaluated the relevant costs of the HTSE plant with a bottom-up approach, obtaining capital costs of 86–197 M\$ and annual operational costs of 11–26 M\$. The opportunity cost, i.e., the loss of revenues due to the electricity not sold but spent to produce hydrogen, is estimated considering 5 years of hourly electricity

Appendix

In this appendix, we reported in detail the estimation of costs for the HTSE plants. Table A and Table B report configuration data from Ref. [11] and other values (used or computed) from other references. Table C reports the code of accounts for the HTSE plants.

price data from 4 countries (France, Germany, Italy, and Romania). For a full year (8760 h) of hydrogen production, the expected opportunity cost is around 30 M\$ for configuration H1, increasing with the number of modules, and reaching 110–150 M\$ for configuration H4. The differences are caused solely by the electricity fluctuations of the countries. Italy has the highest contribution from opportunity cost, followed by France, while Germany’s and Romania’s are almost identical. The minimum LCOH values are 5–6 \$/kg for an average daily production of 17–18 h for all scenarios. Producing as much hydrogen as possible increases the LCOH by 25–30 % because it is better to sell the electricity to the grid for large enough electricity prices. These values for the LCOH are in the ballpark of the ones from renewables and other nuclear but it is larger than fossil fuel-based production.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Federico Tassone: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation. **Stefano Lorenzi:** Visualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Marco Enrico Ricotti:** Funding acquisition, Methodology, Conceptualization, Supervision. **Giorgio Locatelli:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization, Supervision, Validation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Tab. A
Configuration data from Ref. [11].

Variable	Value
Power H1 [MWe]	26.9
Power H2 [MWe]	53.8
Power H3 [MWe]	80.7
Power H4 [MWe]	107.6
Area oh HTSE evaporator H1 [m ²]	198
Area oh HTSE evaporator H2 [m ²]	396
Area oh HTSE evaporator H3 [m ²]	486
Area oh HTSE evaporator H4 [m ²]	577
For HTSE evaporator: tubes & shell in carbon steel	
Area condenser H1 [m ²]	210
Area subcooler H1 [m ²]	20.81
Area condenser H2 [m ²]	321
Area subcooler H2 [m ²]	42.63
Area condenser H3 [m ²]	664
Area subcooler H3 [m ²]	77.06
Area condenser H4 [m ²]	802
Area subcooler H4 [m ²]	93.79
For condenser: tubes & shell in carbon steel	
For subcooler: tubes & shell in carbon steel	

Tab. B
Data retrieved from other references. Underlined values are the ones directly reported by the reference, the others are computed from the available data.

Variable	Value
<u>Reference</u>	[23]
<u>Value reported for TCI</u>	567665510
<u>Ratio DC/TCI</u>	0.704
<u>Ratio Account 1/TCI</u>	0.015
Ratio Account 1/DC	0.021
<u>Ratio Account 31/TCI</u>	0.07
Ratio Account 31/DC	0.0994
<u>Ratio Account 32/TCI</u>	0.07
Ratio Account 32/DC	0.0994
<u>Ratio Account 33/TCI</u>	0.127
Ratio Account 33/DC	0.1804
<u>Ratio Account 34/TCI</u>	0.014
Ratio Account 34/DC	0.0199
<u>Ratio Account 3/TCI</u>	0.281
<u>Value reported for replacement costs</u>	11726402
Ratio Account 41/TCI	0.0207
<u>Value reported for royalties</u>	11191068
Ratio Account 42/TCI	0.0197
<u>Value reported for labor and maintenance</u>	33230336
Ratio Account 43/TCI	0.0585
<u>Value reported for overhead</u>	6170526
Ratio Account 44/TCI	0.0109
<u>Value reported for insurance and taxes</u>	11358934
Ratio Account 45/TCI	0.0200
<u>Reference</u>	[21]
<u>Exponent economy of scale - Reactor/boiler plant</u>	0.6
<u>Exponent economy of scale - Turbine plant</u>	0.8
Exponent assumed for HTSE system	0.6
<u>Reference</u>	[18]
<u>Power requirement of the HTSE stack [MWe]</u>	1000
<u>Value reported for Account 221 [\$2020]</u>	215770000
<u>Value reported for Account 223 [\$2020]</u>	58560000
<u>Value reported for Account 224 [\$2020]</u>	90650000
<u>Value reported for Account 226 [\$2020]</u>	830000
<u>Reference</u>	[19]
From 2020 USD to 2022 USD	1.0388
<u>Reference</u>	[24]
<u>Cost model for shell&tube heat exchanger, given area A [m2]</u>	$C_c = \ln(A) - 0.06395A^2 + 947A + 227.9$
<u>Cost model for pump, given power P [kWe]</u>	$C_p = \ln(P) - 0.03195P^2 + 467.2P + 20480$
<u>Reference</u>	[22]
<u>Site labor cost - feedwater heating system - pag 65 - FOAK</u>	17112917
<u>Site materials cost - feedwater heating system - pag 65 - FOAK</u>	1703455
<u>Total cost - feedwater heating system - pag 65 - FOAK</u>	37796750
Ratio labor/factory cost	0.453
Ratio site material/factory cost	0.045

(continued on next page)

Tab. B (continued)

Variable	Value
Miscellaneous plant equipment subtotal - pag 33 - FOAK	70656254
Total direct costs - pag 33 - FOAK	1187089509
Ratio Account 25/DC	0.0595
Turbine generator cost - FOAK	330612022
Turbine generator cost - NOAK	321562255
FOAK coefficient used for Acc. 232	1028
Other turbine plant equipment - pag 32 - FOAK	40286456
Total turbine plant equipment - pag 32 - FOAK	266443824
Ratio to estimate Acc. 233 as in Note A	0.17
Reference	[25]
Carbon steel factor = 1/1,70 (base case - stainless steel)	0.588

Before the code of account, consider the following notes.

- A. Account 21 and 25 are 10 % and around 6 % of account 2. We can consider all the other accounts to write:
 - i. Account 21 as 10 %/(1–16 %) of the accounts 22 to 25, the fraction is 0,119;
 - ii. Account 25 as 6 %/(1–16 %) of the accounts 22 to 25, the fraction is 0,071.
- B. The reference HTSE plant in Ref. [18] is much larger than the ones considered here. For plants with so many modules, fixed costs of the site are shared among more modules. Here, we assumed an increase of 15 % because of the lower number of modules, which do not benefit as much from cositing economies.

Tab. C

Code of accounts used for the estimation of HTSE costs. All the costs, reported in 2022 \$, are inserted in the last four columns (one for each configuration). The used values or equations are all reported in the previous Tab A and B.

ACCOUNT	METHOD OF ESTIMATION	DATA	MODEL	H1	H2	H3	H4	
1 Capitalized pre-construction costs	Fraction of the DC or TCI	Fraction of DC [23]	0.021	1.28E+06	1.95E+06	2.49E+06	2.96E+06	
2 Capitalized direct cost	Sum of Acc. 21, 22, 23, 24, and 25			6.02E+07	9.13E+07	1.17E+08	1.39E+08	
21 Structures and improvements	Assumed 10 % of DC, see Note A	Fraction of DC	0.119	6021877	9129490	11670768	13869038	
22 H ₂ generation process equipment	Sum of Acc. 221, 222, 223, 224, 225, and 226			50096677	76009665	96925886	115183297	
221 HTSE system	Estimated from literature and corrected with factors	Value in literature (L) [18] Power in literature (P1) [18] Power in this study (P2) Economy of scale (e) [21] Increase due to siting (s), see Note B Inflation (i) [19]	215770000 1000 Tab. A 0.6 1.15 1.0388	$C_{221} = isL \left(\frac{P_2}{P_1} \right)^e$	29449112	44636507	56930495	67656294
222 Feedwater and heat transfer system	Estimated the cost of the HTSE evaporator	Area [m ²] Factory cost (c) [24] Tube material factor (t) [25] Fraction site labor (l) [22] Fraction site materials (m) [22] Inflation (i) [19]	Tab. A Tab. B [24] 0.588 0.453 0.045 1.0388	$C_{222} = ict(1 + l + m)$	169533	334266	407628	480841
223 Sweep gas system	Estimated from literature and corrected with factors	Value in literature [18]	58560000	As Acc. 221	7992492	12114352	15450942	18361925
224 Purification and collection system	Estimated from literature and corrected with factors	Value in literature [18]	90650000	As Acc. 221	12372257	18752835	23917826	28423984
225 Other miscellaneous equipment	Not considered in the study				0	0	0	0
226 Instrumentation and control	Estimated from literature and corrected with factors	Value in literature [18]	830000	As Acc. 221	113281	171702	218993	260252
23 Thermal oil intermediate circuit	Sum of Acc. 231, 232, and 233				515963	721821	1164525	1383117
231 Thermal oil	Assumed 100, 130, 160, and 190 tons @ 2\$/kg				200000	260000	320000	380000

(continued on next page)

Tab. C (continued)

ACCOUNT	METHOD OF ESTIMATION	DATA	MODEL	H1	H2	H3	H4		
232	Heat transfer system equipment	Estimated from literature and corrected with factors	Condenser area [m ²] Subcooler area [m ²] Factory cost of the above (Cc) [24] Oil pump power [kWe] [11] Factory cost pump (Cp) [24] Tube material factor (t) [25] Fraction site labor (l) [22] Fraction site materials (m) [22] FOAK coefficient (f) [22] Inflation (i) [19]	Tab. A Tab. A Tab. B 2.34 Tab. B 0.588 0.453 0.045 1028 1.0388	$C_{232} = if(1 + l + m)(tC_c + C_p)$	237949	352682	668448	793989
233	Piping, tank, and other equipment	Fraction of Acc. 23	Fraction of Acc. 23 [22]	0.178					
24	Electrical equipment	Assumed to be already considered in other accounts			0	0	0	0	
25	Miscellaneous equipment	Estimated from values in literature, assumed 6 % of DC, see Note A	Fraction of DC	0.071	3584256	5433925	6946509	8254931	
3	Capitalized indirect costs	Sum of Acc. 31, 32, 33, 34			2.40E+07	3.64E+07	4.66E+07	5.54E+07	
31	Site preparation	Fraction of the DC or TCI	Fraction of DC [23]	0.0994	5987662	9077617	11604457	13790236	
32	Engineering and design	Fraction of the DC or TCI	Fraction of DC [23]	0.0994	5987662	9077617	11604457	13790236	
33	Contingency and contractor's fee	Fraction of the DC or TCI	Fraction of DC [23]	0.1803	10863329	16469392	21053801	25019429	
34	Legal fee	Fraction of the DC or TCI	Fraction of DC [23]	0.0199	1197532	1815523	2320891	2758047	
The TCI is the sum of accounts 1, 2, and 3					8.55E+07	1.30E+08	1.66E+08	1.97E+08	
4	Annualized O&M and decommissioning costs	Sum of Acc. 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, and 46			1.11E+07	1.68E+07	2.15E+07	2.56E+07	
41	Replacement costs	Estimated from values in literature	Fraction of TCI [23]	0.0207	1766979	2678836	3424515	4069545	
42	Royalties	Estimated from values in literature	Fraction of TCI [23]	0.0197	1686313	2556541	3268178	3883762	
43	Labor and maintenance	Estimated from values in literature	Fraction of TCI [23]	0.0585	5007275	7591298	9704407	11532299	
44	Overhead	Estimated from values in literature	Fraction of TCI [23]	0.0109	929798	1409624	1802007	2141427	
45	Insurance and taxes	Estimated from values in literature	Fraction of TCI [23]	0.0200	1711608	2594889	3317201	3942019	
46	Decommissioning costs	Not considered in the study			0	0	0	0	

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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GLOSSARY

ALFRED: Advanced Lead-cooled Fast Reactor European Demonstrator
ANSELMUS: Advanced Nuclear Safety Evaluation of Liquid Metals Using Systems
AWE: Alkaline Water Electrolysis
BOP: Balance-Of-Plant
CAPEX: Capital Expenditure
CC: Carbon Capture
DC: Direct Cost
FOAK: First-Of-A-Kind
GIF: Gen-IV International Forum
HSB: Hot Standby
HTSE: High-Temperature Steam Electrolysis
IAEA: International Atomic Energy Agency
LFR: Lead-cooled Fast Reactor
LWR: Light Water Reactor
NEA: Nuclear Energy Association
NOAK: Nth-Of-A-Kind
NPP: Nuclear Power Plant
O&M: Operation and Maintenance
OPEX: Operational Expenditure
R&D: Research and Development
SI: Sodium-Iodine
SMR: Small Modular Reactor
TCI: Total Capital Investment
TPH: Total Produced Hydrogen
USD: American Dollar